

Levels of Open Science for Empirical Research Using Software: A Proposal

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Abstract

Open Science involves using new approaches to scientific practice that makes the outputs of research freely available under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction. Empirical research using software involves researchers identifying a problem, gathering data, building a model or writing analysis software, possibly simulating the physical system, analysing results and producing research articles. There are many topics in Open Science that could help a researcher to his or her research more open. However, particularly for those new to Open Science, it can be difficult to get started or even to organise and approach or strategy. This discussion article proposes a set of Levels of Open Science for this area and is aimed at contributing to this emerging debate.

1. Introduction

The general concept of Open Science involves adopting new approaches to scientific practice where the outputs of research are freely available under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction (www.fosteropenscience.eu). Open Science therefore refers to efforts to make the output of research more widely accessible to scientific communities, business sectors, and society more generally (OECD 2015). There are many associated concepts: open access, open research data, open research protocols and notebooks, open access to research materials, open source software, citizen science, open peer review and open collaboration. It is often facilitated by digital technology and open access repositories. The depth and breadth of Open Science can make it difficult for researchers to get started. There is also a “crisis” of reproducibility where scientists are unable to reproduce and build on the work of others due to research outputs being inaccessible (Baker, 2016).

Many research fields develop software to support the empirical investigate of the real world. For example, one might develop a model of a hospital ward to investigate bed management, a manufacturing system to improve production, fluid flow through a pipe to determine throughput, wind turbine blades to develop the most efficient shape, etc. Generally, a researcher identifies a problem, gathers data, builds a model or writes analysis software, possibly uses it to simulates the physical system and analyses results. The researcher writes these up and publishes an article in a conference or journal. The model is typically created in software which may be written in a programming language (e.g., Java, C++, etc.), utilise some API/library available in that language or developed in some domain specific software tool. Some models may use some complex environment that involve complex deployment (e.g., the model is written in a language using a library that requires complex implementation in Windows, LINUX, etc.) Others may be distributed across many computers or use many computers to perform experimentation.

The question in the above is how to make the outputs (the data, model, software, results, etc.) open. There is much written about each aspect of Open Science (e.g., Open Access, Open Data, etc.). However, especially for those that are new to Open Science, given the opportunities in the above paragraph, it can be difficult to conceptualise these in some form of Open Science “strategy” for

empirical research involving software. This short note therefore proposes a conceptual model based on increasing levels of openness.

2. Levels of Open Science for Empirical Research Using Software

Figure 1 shows the levels that we are proposing and a brief description in terms of the impact on a published article.

Openness	Open Science Level	A researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, model and results...	Effort
↓	Level 0 – Not Open	The article is behind a paywall and cannot be accessed without payment or some form of subscription.	↓
	Level 1 – Open Access	The article is published under Gold or Green Open Access. Researchers can freely access the article. However, the data, model and results are only described in the article.	
	Level 2 – Open Data	As Level 1 + the researcher openly publishes the data, software and results by depositing them in an Open Access Repository following Open Data practices.	
	Level 3 – Open Reproducibility	As Level 2 + the researcher documents the study using a standard reporting process, documents the model to specify how it should be implemented and run, potentially seeks to have some form of independent reproducibility certificate.	
	Level 4 – Open Environment	As Level 3 + the researcher installs the model and associated artefacts on a virtual machine or virtual environment.	
	Level 5 – Open Infrastructure	As Level 4 + the researcher deploys the model and associated artefacts with a Science Gateway to allow other researchers to run the model as simply as possible.	

Figure 1: Levels of Open Science for Empirical Research Using Software

Level 0: Not Open

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, model and results. The article may have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. However, the article is behind a paywall and cannot be accessed without payment or some form of subscription.

Level 1: Open Access

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, software and results. The article may have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. Other researchers can access the paper without payment as the article is published under (for example) *Gold* open access where the journal provides free open access to that article or *Green* open access where the author self-archives the article, typically in some institutional Open Access Repository with some agreement from the publisher.

Level 2: Open Data

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, software and results. The article will have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. The article is published under Gold or Green Open Access. The data, model and results are published openly in some Open Access Repository. The software might be published openly on a dedicated platform such as GitHub.

Level 3: Open Reproducibility

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, software and results. The article will have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. The article is published under Gold or Green Open Access. The data, model and results are published openly. The researcher fully documents their model and associated software using a recognised reporting format and creates a guide to using and running the software. The researcher applies and is awarded a certificate of reproducibility from a recognised body (e.g., the RCR from ACM).

Level 4: Open Environment

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, software and results. The article will have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. The article is published under Gold or Green Open Access. The data, model and results are published openly. The researcher fully documents their model and associated software using a recognised reporting format and creates a guide to using and running the software. The researcher applies and is awarded a certificate of reproducibility from a recognised body. The researcher also creates a virtual machine and installs the model, data and associated software to simplify implementation.

Level 5: Open Infrastructure

The researcher publishes an article about a study that describes the aim, background literature, approach, data, software and results. The article will have a DOI that facilitates search discovery. The article is published under Gold or Green Open Access. The data, model and results are published openly. The researcher fully documents their model and associated software using a recognised reporting format and creates a guide to using and running the software. The researcher applies and is awarded a certificate of reproducibility from a recognised body. The researcher also creates a virtual machine and installs the model, data and associated software. This is deployed on a digital infrastructure and accessed through a science gateway, a web-based portal or front end created to access and run the model. This requires more work from the researcher but is perhaps the simplest way for other researchers to access and run the software as all they need to do is understand how the web-based portal works.

3. Discussion

The above conceptual model of Open Science has been created based on experiences in Modelling & Simulation (M&S) (Taylor, et al., 2017), the use of e-Infrastructures for M&S (Taylor, 2019) and the development of e-Infrastructures in Africa (Kashefi, et al. 2018). In M&S authors typically publish studies that are, for the most part, at Level 1 (Open Access). Researchers are keen to make their work more open. There are several simulation study documentation guides (e.g., STRESS (Monks, et al., 2019), ODD (Grimm, et al., 2010), etc.) and professional bodies are beginning to issue certificates of reproducibility (e.g., the Replicated Computational Results (RCR) from ACM). In research supported by large-scale e-Infrastructures such as those developed by the EC, Open Science is more widely practiced, particularly in terms of software supported by computational infrastructure. In the AI and Software Engineering communities there is some advice on Open Science that could be applied more widely to fields using software in research but there is also an arguable lack of structure to these as the focus tends to be on the approach (i.e., Open Access, Open Data, etc.) This is further compounded by institutional support focusing understandably on Open Access and some aspects of Open Data – there are far fewer researchers involved in empirical software-based research. There is also the issue

that many institutions in developing countries are developing Open Science strategies based on these general experiences. The question is how to get started and how to organise.

Discussions with researchers in this area often lead to the following questions.

- How do I make my paper open?
- How do I make the research described in my paper open (e.g., data, software, etc.)?
- How do I make it easy for someone else to reproduce my results?
- How do I make it easy for someone else to use my software?
- How do I make it easy for someone else to access my specialist computing resources?
- How do I make it as easy as possible for someone else to access all the research in my article?
- How do I become an Open Scientist?

Our Levels attempt to organise a structured response. Making an article as open as possible is at Level 1. Level 2 is when a researcher deposits data in an open access repository where the data is referenced by a DOI. Software can be deposited in a specialist repository for software (i.e., GitHub) and also linked with a DOI. In Level 3 a researcher documents the use of the software and data for others to independently reproduce results. The use of software in research, particularly when developing the software itself, brings some interesting challenges. It can be difficult for an independent scientist to take someone else's software and use it, even if documentation is available. Dependencies, operating system differences and version control of APIs and libraries can make what seems to be a simple implementation difficult. Therefore, in Level 4 a researcher uses containerisation or virtual machines to try to simplify this – others install container or virtual machine that already has the software installed (i.e., an open environment). Admittedly this requires knowledge to do this but it is becoming more and more straightforward. Level 5 reflects experience with e-Infrastructures. Here a web-based frontend, or Science Gateway, is created to make access to the software as easy as possible. Level 5 might also include access to high performance computing that might be available in the open infrastructure. Overall effort increases from Level 1 to 5 as does openness.

4. Conclusions

A longer article is being developed that gives more justification to the levels and an illustrative case study. However, for now we wish to disseminate our conceptual model so that we can use this as a way of structuring discussion in this area.

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